

Transitions in modernist factory planning in São Paulo 1945 – 1955 : the influence of British and North-american design ideas.

American factory architecture with notions of being “lean and mean”.

“Architects who undertake the design of factories are faced with considerations different in many aspects from those to which they have been accustomed. These differences are perhaps more in degree than in kind, for the same fundamental principles apply to all types of architecture. In the industrial field they are simplified, are more clear-cut and uncompromising than in most others. Here function is the dominant factor, followed closely by economy. No esthetic consideration can prevail unless it is completely consonant with these other factors. This is a matter not arguable, especially with industrial clients. Such a concept is really very wholesome. The type of discipline involved might very well improve almost any practitioner of our art”.¹ Frederick J. Woodbridge AIA

(Architect- Evans, Moore & Woodbridge) Architectural Record, January. 1941.

Albert Kahn, Architect “Producer Of Production Lines”

It was on Thursday, February 5, 1939, that Albert Kahn received a telephone call from the Glenn L. Martin Company, Baltimore. “Can you furnish plans quickly enough for us to put up a 440,000 sq. ft. building by May 1?” That was quite an order: a mammoth aircraft factory building to be ready for use in 84 days. But Kahn was prepared to answer, “Yes”²

The conception of a “Fordist” architecture as a ‘speeding-up’ of the factory

The Van Nelle cigarette, coffee and tea factory in Rotterdam, during the 1920’s provided an innovative design repertoire with the volumetric composition of glazed walls and arranged forms with up to ten floors of glass and concrete in a geometric variety of rectangular blocks, circle quadrants and diametric arcs. During that decade, these innovations provided a certain design preeminence for European factory buildings in general and more specifically for the Dutch architectural firm of Brinkmann & van der Vlugt.³ Later, in the early war years of the 1940’s the American professional journal, the ‘Architectural Record’, included one article by a north-american architect Roland Wank, who as well as himself, cited other architectural colleagues already considered ‘pioneers’ in modernist factory architecture. These included Peter Behrens with his turbine Factory in Berlin in 1909, Eric Mendelsohn and his hat factory in Luckenwalde, Germany built between 1921-23 and Robert Maillart’s Benet Factory in Barcelona in 1924⁴. The turbine factory in Berlin would appeal to an international fascination with new mechanical technology whereby power stations and their turbines became “the new cathedrals” as in the UK case of the Battersey Power Station by Sir Giles Scott.

Behrens steel roof trusses took on an added importance for the fabrication, maintenance and storage not only of the turbines but also the new aviation machines which required ever increasing roof heights and especially spans. The Eric Mendelsohn hat factory provided its peculiar formal representation of ventilation control, while the Benet Factory in Barcelona provided new unencumbered north light monitors in 1924. The New York based architect Wank, as in the case of all authors, could be criticized for his eventual omissions such as the curtain-wall innovation of the Fagus shoe factory by Walter Gropius and Adolf Meyer at Alfeld-an-der-Linhe in Germany (1911-25)⁵. In Holland in the twenties other important designs for a modernist factory design paradigm were produced including the Rokin building in Amsterdam (1926).

In the industrial architecture of the thirties, however, Europe was already seen to be incorporating north American factory design influences. In the United Kingdom the Architectural Record in February 1940 presented a project for new chemical factory, in Buckinghamshire, England as designed by the architect Raymond McGrath in 1939⁶. In this project McGrath had already prepared for war time bombing, with air-raid shelters already installed at basement level. In a more formal sense, the McGrath design could be understood as attempting to “americanize” Van Nelle. In the UK plant for 600

Fig. 1 – the Van Nelle tobacco, coffee and tea factory in Rotterdam 1925-31. Brinkmann & van der Vlugt

Fig. 2 – The European Van Nelle factory site plan showing an ample provision of recreational and sports facilities for factory employees. source: Geurst, 1994.

patterns developed and studied. In addition, the broad policies of a company control questions such as centralization or decentralization of various manufacturing operations and employee facilities, which may bear directly upon building design.”⁷

Plot plan indicates extent of employees' playfields. A, offices; B, service and recreation area; C, manufacturing area; D, playfield equipment pavilion; E, bowling greens, tennis courts, football and cricket fields, etc.

employees, the architect still followed the provision of Van Nelle type employee benefits with approximately half the site given over to playing fields and recreational uses. Fig.3 At the same time, the volumetric use circular forms, diametric arcs were inscribed in a lower building mass. The UK buildings were also of reinforced concrete frame construction with pre-cast slab facings on main facades and brick on other elevations and north light roof slabs. But the american design character could be seen especially in the height of the factory now designed on a low horizontal block basis with basement facilities in addition to the longer horizontal rectangular forms. The differences with previous factory design characteristics began with building function increasingly tied to an unimpeded flow pattern design for mass fabrication. In a 1941 review of architectural factory architecture by the Architectural Record, began with the following introduction: “... an axiom of production engineers states that, for economy and efficiency, ‘the plant must be built around the process’....”.

“It is essential, therefore that a factory design be first considered as a problem in production. Requirements ought to be researched for every department, operations charted, basic flow

Fig. 3 – Chemical Factory Bucks., UK by Raymond McGrath ARIBA in 1939 with air-raid shelter basements and ample recreational facilities.

In the same year of 1941 the AR journal published an article by the designer and builder H.K.Ferguson dealing with new design techniques now required by changed economic conditions of war time production. According to Ferguson, new design guidelines follow the "manufacturers desire for large clear areas unobstructed by columns, partition walls, stairs, elevators, etc. Such space readily houses a proper "flow sheet" arrangement of equipment. It also facilitates later changes in production layouts, as required by research, new products, availability of improved and higher speed machinery, and varying needs for raw and finished storage. Improved possibilities for transportation, supervision and inspection, in single story buildings, with clear floor space, are also very helpful. Column spacings are today never less than 40ft (12.2m); often 200ft (61m) or more in at least one direction".⁸

The logic of speeding up production line extended to factory building itself and Ferguson commented the benefits of prefabrication, in the following terms "... To any manufacturer, standardization and speed are closely related. In consequence, there is a renewed interest in the better types of standardized one-story industrial buildings which are available for quick completion. Such structures are easily dressed up with an attractive exterior architectural treatment, or to conform to adjoining existing plant buildings. They are ordinarily delivered, ready to occupy, in 60 working days."⁹

For the American industrial architect Albert Kahn, the architect working in industry did not have to opt for "off the peg easily dressed up" solutions but instead could competently begin to follow and use the prime company values of the industrial client themselves : organization, efficiency, and speed.¹⁰ The Detroit based firm of Albert Kahn Inc. Architects and Engineers emphasized the speed of production flow even in cases where assembly did not involve a moving line as the Ohio Steel Foundry Co. building or the factory for the Toledo Scale Company at Toledo, Ohio both reviewed by the AR journal in January and February 1941. Fig 4b The firms design specialty seemed to concentrate of assembly work in both aircraft and automobile plants.

Their clients included Curtiss Wright and Pratt & Whitney and parts plants as well as Chrysler Corp, Ford and General Motors / Chevrolet Automobile and aircraft factories.¹¹ The economy of speeding up the productive cycle had already been apparent not only to Henry Winslow Taylor but more especially to Henry Ford, after the recession and financial squeeze on the Ford Motor Company in the early twenties.¹² Speeding up the consumption-production cycle was at the origins of the Fordist six dollar day but what might be termed the "mechanics of fordism" involved immedi-

Fig. 4 – The initial flow chart design for organizing auto plant assembly plant flow operations and their factory design parameters. Flow process design as applied by the Albert Kahn office for a factory project for the Toledo Scale Company. source: Reid, 1951,2.4.

ately re-channeling individual workers savings capacity through the spread of financial hire-purchase economics which began in the United States in 1918 and 1919. If Henry Ford became the spokesman for a new mode of industrial production it could also be argued that might be termed the 'Mechanics of Fordism' for 'speeding-up' industrial economies were more widely known by the head of Ford's rival in the General Motors Corporation, Alfred Sloan. 'Sloanism', in the nineteen-twenties and thirties, implied new company standards of planning, programming and logical demand prevision, with standards for financial controls (including those on the profit rate return on invested capital), inventory stock management, decentralized engineering and distribution operations and personnel management.¹³ While the diversity of GM product lines contrasted with Ford's initial single product for the Model T and after 1928 the later Model A cars, Sloan's company mechanics repeated and perfected Ford's insistence on transportation economies and 'wasted time' elimination. But it was Ford who expressed the implications for factory architecture De-

scribing company operations in the late twenties, Henry Ford commented: "We recently established a new type of assembly plant, which has only one story with transporters laid-out in such a manner as to eliminate as much as possible transport and handling. This new type of factory means greater efficiency. Production increased without an increase in labor. In the Chicago factory the greatest distance that any material travels without fabrication is six meters – from the incoming rail wagon to the first transporter."¹⁴

For a new automobile factory in Detroit in the forties design began with machine template layouts and elaborate CPM flow charts integrating parts production and assembly operations began in a planned movement based on unencumbered relations of flow and velocity. Line speed and the timing of material flows and fabrication operations had still to encounter layout problems of machinery and product obsolescence with the consequent need for retooling and change in fabrication flows. These could be dealt with by incorporating external factory expansion provision and ample internal bay widths and distances between columns. Long linear flows minimizing vertical movement reduced multi story building costs while the fascination with speed and material flow seemed to spread to almost all aspects of factory architecture.

Speeding up accessibility and circulation patterns for material, labor and products emphasized the factory as a long linear or aggregated-linear form in single or multiple bays providing the unencumbered space for "housing" actual and future factory production flows. Material flows, employee entrance and exit movements and other visiting personnel flow routes should be designed around the primacy of the production line flows. Service flows dealing with everything from toilets and food to garbage and cleaning material etc. had to eliminate or at least minimize cross movement.

The long linear form could have an aesthetic dimension as in the long line production solutions suggested in the Ford Willow Run Bomber Plant in Detroit or the GM factory in Flint Michigan in the 1940s. Factory form would mean elongated single or aggregated bays as used when bending or folding the main product flow of fabrication. Speeding up production flows led to a 'fordist' design predominance for single story unencumbered floor space which in turn led to new programmatic requirements for mezzanine and basement production and service areas. Fig 5

For employees still divided by blue and white collar distinctions, one crucial issue for both groups was punching the time clock with variations in the desired location of this control of paid-labor at the moment of arrival in the factory grounds or from the management viewpoint, a preference for time-

Column spacings are today never less than 40 ft.; often 200 ft. or more in at least one direction. Above are typical plan schemes

Fig. 5 - Design alternatives for factory layouts with mezzanine and basement alternatives. The efficiency of "everything under one roof" would favor the large scale production plants. *ibid* 47,51.

clock location at the point of contact with the production line or specific work station. In the nineteen thirties and forties union/management strikes and negotiations led to the widespread acceptance of the "portal to portal pay" measured on the points of entry and exit from the factory building itself.

Promoting the notion of "speeding up" to the point of cultural obsession, General Motors by 1940 had located their new Allison engine plant for aircraft, designed by the Austin Co. specifically in the town of Speedway, Indiana, near Indianapolis.¹⁵ The speedway for racing car competitions or often seen in testing facilities also was used as the basic design motif in the organization of the multi-functional complex of activities proposed by the architectural firm of

Saarinen & Swanson when invited by Alfred Sloan, president of General Motors, to prepare the project of the new GM Technical Center near Detroit. With its "speedway" enclosing the gigantic seven acre artificial lake this speedway motif integrated Saarinen's major architectural buildings for administration, research laboratories, advanced engineering, and styling section design studios which were reviewed in the *Architectural Record* in November 1945. See Fig 6a. If speeding up activity interrelations became a principle design obsession the building reviews of this professional journal, many examples illustrate the diversity of design questions considered.

Fig. 6— The Saarinen & Swanson design for the General Motors Technical Center near Detroit 1945 and speeding up factory accident escape routes using engineering duct design solutions. Reid, 346-9, 343

Speeding up toilet time was one such issue raised in a design brief by Albert Kahn Associated Architects and Engineers Study as published in a paper on "Factory Design for Low-cost Production" which appeared in the *Architectural Record* AR in November 1945. In this paper the Kahn viewpoint was stated in the following terms"

"We believe the production floor should be kept as clear as possible of all non-production obstructions for the sake of cleanliness and adaptability and flexibility.

Toilets on the production floor may stand in the way of a needed new conveyor, and lockers may block the path of a projected new production line. The necessary corners and angles formed by lockers and similar facilities are also dirt catchers and elimination of them reduces the housekeeping burden on the production floor. Sometimes because of rock, ground water, or other soil conditions it is not practical to provide a basement. In such cases we recommend locating employee facilities on a mezzanine and bringing the men down to the production floor instead of up from the basement. A mezzanine layout follows the same essential pattern as the basement design...The reason we prefer a basement to a mezzanine is that to get necessary clearances it is generally advisable to go so high with the mezzanine that considerably more steps are required to reach toilets and lockers located there than in the basement. Not only are the extra steps fatiguing to the workers, but it should also be kept in mind that if conveniently located facilities can reduce by only one minute a day the time spent by a worker in going to and from toilets, the sum total of savings in a plant of 6,000 men adds up to 100 hours a day which would otherwise be non-production expense."¹⁶

As well as speeding up toilet time (p.141 166) Kahn had his engineering sections also interested in other aspects of speed. Speeding up gravity was another such design issue dealt with by H.D.Unwin, a mechanical engineer in the same Detroit firm of Albert Kahn Associated Architects and Engineers, Inc.. In an article on "Industrial Piping" in the *Architectural Record* in February 1943. Unwin considered storage facilities for gasoline and oils of different types including lubricating oils, and cutting oils for steel, aluminum, magnesium, bronze, and brass, with high military value in war-time, Unwin wrote: *"In order to keep tank cars and tank trucks rolling, extensive unloading stations are built which will empty the tanks in a minimum of time. Gravity unloading is too slow. By using pumps it is often possible to release a railroad car within 60 to 80 minutes from the time it is first spotted."*¹⁷

In other areas of industrial laboratory architecture, the possibility of industrial accidents or war-time sabotage brought speeding up considerations to fast escape routes using new ducts as developed by mechanical and ventilation design. In November 1945, the *Architectural Record* provided a photo illustration of a young lady emerging from one such a duct in a review of a new Firestone Research Laboratory for the Firestone Tire & Rubber Co. in Akron, Ohio as designed by the firm of Voorhees, Walker, Foley & Smith architects and engineers.¹⁸ See Fig 6b.

mass, velocity and consequently force. As portrayed in the design of engineering laboratories for automobile and aircraft factories "speeding up" could lead to disequilibrium and destructive vibrations.

These occurred not only in the industries products but also in the mechanical nature of the production line itself. In their car and aircraft products Ford and GM often designed control mechanisms for disequilibrium and destructive vibrations. In the Fordist factory setting, a Kahn based design code would suggest careful attention to the control and management of process velocity with particular attention to the environmental tolerances of the work processes as a preventive measure to avoid 'bad vibrations' particularly among the work-force.

São Paulo and the peculiarities of brazilian fordism

In one important source of information on modern architecture in São Paulo, the first architect responsible for a modern architectural building in this metropolis, was Julio de Abreu Junior and not Gregori Warchavchik as more suggested by other sources. According to Xavier, Lemos & Carona (1983, 01), Abreu Jr. worked extensively in São Paulo in the 1920's but was more concerned with industrial construction than with his modernist apartment building on Angelica Avenue completed in 1927.

Little appears to be known of this industrial work. In the survey of 'Modern Architecture' in this metropolis presented by these same authors, industrial architecture received relatively limited attention. In a universe of 211 examples of 'modernism', factory architecture received 7 mentions. It should be said that other functional categories, including churches and also hospitals, received even less emphasis. This paper is not concerned with the criteria used in this survey selection although the cited text does make repeated references to prize-winning awards and honorable mentions in Architectural 'Bienal' competitions. However, it may seem strange in Latin America's largest industrial agglomeration, to have so few celebrated examples of factory modernism. This situation could even be possibly attributed to the normal partiality of tendencies and interests in academic architectural history. In relation to colonial architecture, Menezes and Rodrigues (1986 p.17) cited Rui Carita who criticized the fact that colonial military architecture was often treated as an academic subject of limited stature between the more important classifications of de religious and civil architecture. Paraphrasing Carita it may be felt that 20th century industrial architecture in Brazil has been treated as a type of "parenthesis" between public and private residential architecture on the one hand and buildings designed for tertiary sector functions including government on the other.

Fig. 9 – The now demolished Duchesne Biscuit Factory Guarulhos SP by Oscar Niemeyer and Hélio Uchoa 1950
source: Xavier, 1983,23

American industrial methods and factories arrived with the American corporations in the 1920's. Henry Ford had visited São Paulo and Recife in 1919 and in the twenties was responsible for new rubber production plants in the Tapajós river basin in the Amazon with its new company towns appropriately named Fordlandia and Belterra with the largest town square in Brazil not far from the port of Santarém. As well as avoiding questions on the internationalization of the Fordist salary at US\$6 dollar day at the end of the first world war the company had little difficulty in applying US prohibition laws inside its own company gates in its Fordlândia and Belterra rubber plants in the late twenties and early thirties.

However many elements of Fordism as described by Sloan would arrive in Brazil only half a century later with military government and the massification of hire-purchase finance or 'consórcio' arrangements in the sixties for a consuming middle-class. It is also comparatively recent the appearance of billboards inside the São Caetano GM factory urging Brazilian workers to buy company cars through a consórcio car installment plan. see Fig.8.

Lipietz and the French regulation school and the characterization within 20th century Latin America raising the possibility of Brazilian Fordism as an extension of work practices inherited from an antecedent phase called "bloody" Taylorism. It could be argued that this type of Taylorism was always endemic to most types of capitalist industrial development. Gramsci repeated and extended a belief in Taylorism into a new Fordist era.²² Fordism in industry led to:

"a continual reduction of the economic function of transport and trade to the level of a genuinely subaltern activity of production. Indeed, it has led to the attempt to absorb these activities into productive activity itself. Recall here the experiments conducted by Ford and to the economies made by his firm through direct management of transport and distribution of the product. These economies affected production costs and permitted higher wages and lower selling prices." While the economics of the change were clear the political consequences were more nebulous:

"... In America rationalisation has determined the need to elaborate a new type of man suited to the new type of work and productive process. This elaboration is still only in its initial phase and therefore (apparently) still idyllic. It is still at the stage of psycho-physical adaptation to the new industrial structure, aimed for through high wages."

In more practical terms new modes of industrial work were presented as a means of "speeding up" all

types of change. The notion of "speeding-up" Brazilian industrialization achieved a formal political status when the development slogan "fifty years in five" was adopted by the Federal Government of Juscelino Kubitschek in the second part of the nineteen-fifties. Import-substitution in many senses was attempting to instill a sense of nationalist pride based on endogenous industrialization aimed at "speeding-up" of production chains and their market inter-relations.²³ In the academic literature on development after the 2nd World War, third world national economies were to be treated as aircraft engines, tearing down runways in order to achieve the development goal of "take-off" in the Kuznets "airpeed" model of dealing with under-development economies. Fordist speeding-up seemed to become a discourse model frequently more useful off than on the factory floor.

In the Brazilian city and regional planning literature, paved roads for automobiles after the second world war meant much more than simply speeding-up accessibility in the city. Since the twenties and the Agache plan for Rio de Janeiro the "express-ways" had appeared as a justification for the functionalist zoning of industrial areas separate from workers residential areas. In many senses the "express-way" separation of labor in production and labor in reposition and reproduction ended a period where the company suburb, town or industrial district gives way to a more complex industrial agglomeration based on enlarged scales of production, more intensive in its use of materials and mechanical and electrical equipment and more diverse in its creation and development of markets. (This does not contradict a parallel tendency for the continuation of the company-town form of urbanization as in the cases of specialization, remoteness and/or the particular use of natural resources, as mentioned by Crawford,²⁴) In different countries "speeding-up" the city could take on peculiar national expressions.

In the US, the stream-lined and modernist "express-ways" sometimes became "free-ways" as portrayed in Richard Neutra's proposals for "Rush City" in 1939 pre-figured an urban version of the myth of "the open road". In the UK the search for faster accessibility in the city for an ever-increasing car traffic load led in the sixties to an increase in the hierarchical capacity and access sophistication of urban roads which seems to have reached a high point in the work of Colin Buchanan while Peter Hall would show the unparalleled expansion of the London urban area with the automobile expansion of the cities periphery.²⁵ In Brazil in 1945 the federal government published the First National Road Plan with route map proposals for phased road paving beginning in the large urban agglomerations in Brazil's south east. Subsequent information tends to suggest a close correlation be-

tween the extension of paved roads (and radio reception) in rural states and out-migration especially from Brazil's north-east region going to the large metropolitan centers in the southeast and especially to São Paulo. In this part of the country new road pavement programs were presented in populist terms by governors such as Jânio Quadros or Ademar de Barros for whom faster accessibility reduced costs and lowered the cost of living. Road paving also helped an inedited demographic expansion for the São Paulo metropolis where "speeding up" might refer to the increasing growth rates of the city population.

Other examples of "speeding-up" as regards the building of the factory building itself. Accelerating construction time for new production plants had become a wartime necessity in the USA. When reviewing the important factory architecture contributions of Oscar Niemeyer in the Duchen biscuit plant in São Paulo and his CTA Structures Laboratory building the projects themselves the north american war speed literature does seem relevant, particularly when discussing the important engineering contributions of Niemeyer's partner the civil engineer Joaquim Cardoso. In the United States concrete structures where columns, load bearing beams and shell as they merged into a single product were not innovations in themselves, not even when the products of a single movable form, repeating in series the production of form based linear factory structural elements. As well as the work of the Albert Kahn office, other patented systems already existed including a Roberts and Schaefer system known as the "barrel-shell" or Z-D type of roof construction. What was innovative was the treatment of the concrete form in a new speed technique for thin shell concrete structures: "With the idea of saving critical materials, keeping down costs, and also of developing a form of concrete construction which could be put up with great speed, Albert Kahn Associated Architects and Engineers and Mahony-Troast Company, contractors, developed, after considerable study, the now famous "warspeed" construction.

Fig. 10 – The "warspeed" method of thin shell concrete construction with travelling form work as developed by the Albert Kahn Office 1941.

A system of cantilever slab design was nothing new and had long since been discarded for so-called modern forms of concrete construction. What was new, however, and very successful, was the concept of building the structural system about the form work rather than designing first the structure and then somehow the form work which would enable it to be built. ... a system of form work was scientifically developed-form work which was drawn over previously laid rails by tractors and which could be used over and over again to form each succeeding unit of construction."²⁶

In Brazil immediately after 2nd World War the overall CTA project (centro Técnico de Aeronautica) at the Brazilian Airforce base at São José dos Campos in the state of São Paulo was to be the location for many Oscar Niemeyer / Joaquim Cardoso design innovations. The structures laboratory at the professional engineering school within the CTA complex began life as a simple elliptical form seen in an early scale model of Niemeyer's initial project. As design work progressed this form changed, most probably for functionalist reasons, but led to a new ribbed form, reminiscent of the Kahn design with its 'war-speed' method of construction.²⁷ This impression increases when Niemeyer and Cardoso design the new biscuit factory plant for the Duchen company in 1950. In relation to the structural elements most architectural comment stresses the plastic possibilities of reinforced concrete as seen in highly visible double curved frame structural elements which characterized the now demolished Duchen factory.²⁸ However this form was in fact a subsidiary design condition after a long linear factory form for a production line process had been located on this difficult triangular sloping site. The externalizing of the double curved frame structural elements also implied a "cleaner" interior surface and reinforced the long linear rectangular form. It could be argued that this solution has modernist parallels with the SOM 'inside-out' design notion already emphasized in a review of the Kimberly-Clark Corporation plant at Neenah, Wisconsin published in March 1941, which had been designed by the architecture and engineering firm Skidmore, Owings and Merrill. In that review the AR commented that the plant "is actually turned 'inside-out'. Walls and ceiling are flush inside instead of outside... The fine clean appearance (of Machine Building No.3) could be viewed as the result of novel economics rather than "art". The tight furred ceiling protected the product against dirt...."²⁹ Curiously, the exterior ribbed curved concrete frame elements and the long "clean" factory lines had already come together in his contemporary project for the engineering professional school and structures laboratory in the CTA project mentioned earlier see Fig.11.

Fig. 11 – a,b the engineering professional school and structures laboratory in the CTA project, São José dos Campos, SP
Oscar Niemeyer, 1950

Fig. 12 a – The initial scale model of the Niemeyer project for the CTA project in São José dos Campos
Fig. 12 b – An Initial design for the Volta Redonda steel plant as rejected by the modernist Attila Lima
sources: Penedo 96 Ackel 96.

Fig. 13 – The Jaguaré Industrial Center in São Paulo SP. Henrique Dumont Villares 1941-1947.

"Speeding up" the city by reducing the number of crossing points seems to have been one more issue which began to affect layout plans during the forties. At the beginning of the design work on the CTA project it is also curious to note the overall regular orthogonal layout plan in the scale model used to illustrate the sites relationship to the definitive route map for the then proposed Via Dutra regional highway. see Fig.12 The curiosity is in the similarity with an initial layout plan for the new steel complex in the state company town plan in 1941. This initial CSN plan gave way to more modernist layouts by Atílio Correa Lima³⁰ and this aspect of Niemeyers initial project conception for the CTA were later abandoned in the rival proposals during the CTA design competition, as shown by Penedo (1997, pp36-39).

It is tempting to suggest that in some respects these project changes seem to represent part of a paradigm shift where Brazilian modernism leaves more than breaks with the Belles Artes tradition of formal regularity admitted by previous generations of city beautiful architects and engineers who could organically juxtapose Garden City pretensions with urban neo-classical regularity as permitted both by the Raymond Unwin Town Planning Manual³¹ and by the "American Vitruvius" of Peet e Hegeman. In the 1940's this could still be seen in contemporary industrial real estate development projects in São Paulo. In the cities western limits urban expansion signified a transposition of the Pinheiros river valley and the localization of the Jaguaré Industrial Center as described and proposed by Henrique Dumont Villares in the late forties. The Jaguaré project is an interesting example of a combined industrial and residential development following a paradigm of English industrial garden suburbs still present at this time in the work of Patrick Abercrombie and also in the previous design ideas of Raymond Unwin and of Barry Parker, who had worked for the City of São Paulo Improvements Company, during the first world war. In São Paulo, this heritage assumed a more modernist perspective in the writings of Prof.Dr.Luis Anhaia Mello founder of the University of São Paulo architectural school in 1947 and who also worked as a consultant of the Cia City. Curiously the plan for the USP campus as inscribed in the Villares plan for Jaguaré portrays a plea for neoclassical regularity.

Recreation and Labor Reposition moves outside Fordist Factory design.

The suggestion that the 1940's were a transitional period in design solutions with differences between generations and also with differences between American and European variants for a more intensified industrial production. The regulation of portal

to portal pay and of the paid and unpaid time onsite at the plant led to a pronounced reduction in factory lunch breaks and recreational activity now condemned in the post-Pullman industrialists mind as 'paternalistic' in management-labor relations. In 1946 in the US one factory architect, Ronald Wank, would declare: "Right now in the larger industries both management and labor seem to consider it bad form for industry to offer any employee facilities or services unless they were first demanded and bitterly fought for by the unions".³² Where possible recreation facilities were soon seen, after the war, as an off-site problem to be solved by the city. The elimination of recreational provision also provided another source of economy.

European practice followed an alternative path as can be seen in the ample recreational provision in the Van Nelle project and the sports and recreation facilities also considered in the McGrath chemical plant in the England in the late 1930's as mentioned earlier in this paper. In Europe inter-war industrial and public relations development used increasingly similar design objective to "evoke in employees or clients a "feeling of pride and personal attachment" toward the plant, the company and its products. Recreational facilities and landscaping became important components of strategies for promoting the company image. This might be increasingly difficult to do for employees especially in the US factories where the evolution of fordist labor-management relationship in its "lean and mean" confrontational form, was seen in the bitter disputes in the white-collar/blue-collar thirties strikes in the GM car plants as in Flint, Michigan, in 1937, at the same time as building a new brazilian assembly plant in São Caetano São Paulo. In Brazil both European and North American tendencies for the maintenance or exclusion can be seen at the same time. The European pharmaceutical company Bayer in the early fifties installed a new company industrial suburb on a 'green field' site in Belford Roxo on the outskirts of Rio de Janeiro with access to the new Via Dutra Highway with housing for key workers and ample provision of recreational areas. Further along the Via Dutra Highway in direction towards São Paulo the steel town of Volta Rodunda designed by Atílio Correa Lima at the beginning of the 1940's does include company town type recreational, housing etc type provision for the CSN workers.

Similar provision had already been planned by the New York firm Town Planning Associates run by Paul Lester and the exiled spanish architect and co-founder of the Spanish GATEPAC, Luis Sert and for the State industrial company town FNM (Fábrica Nacional de Motores) at Xerêm in the local author-

ity area of Duque de Caxias in the state of Rio de Janeiro in 1945³³ While the FNM and CSN projects might announce remoteness from existing urban areas as a justification for the ample employee facilities, there are many other examples from Brazil, in less remote urban areas, where employee provision was or wasn't on the architects agenda when designing factory facilities. In the same town of São José dos Campos where Niemeyer worked on the CTA project, the automobile company General Motores, later in 1959, would locate its second São Paulo plant which also showed no recreational facilities. However in the Parahyba Textile factory complex on the outskirts of this same town of São José dos Campos, a complex variety of modernist buildings in a company town setting included in the 1950's, a model house for factory managers by a new generation of modernist architects from the Mackenzie school of architecture in São Paulo including Carlos Millan, L.R.Carvalho Franco e Sidney Fonseca. The same company sponsored a series of modernist projects by the Rino Levi Architects firm including the following projects: the Olivio Gomes Residence, a company 'workers market' commercial facility, housing units for the Parahyba Tecelagem farm workers at Monte Alegre, a company school for the children of the Monte Alegre farm workers, an experimental small church for the farm almost without a cross, two projects for a larger church for a workers residential area adjoining the main factory complex, a health center, crèche and junior school for the same residential area as well as two and three bedroom workers housing units in a ground floor back-to-back formation. The same residential project by Reno Levi shows the ample inclusion of sports facilities, see Fig14. thus following a British, German French and Italian company town policy with the retention of recreational facilities, even were the residential necessity has been subsumed by the town of São José dos Campos.

While firms such as Parahyba Tecelagem or Bayer in Brazil would favor workers housing and recreational benefits North-american practice shows an increasing concern with limiting the concern with workers benefits. In the US, after the 2nd world war, these questions were now subject to management-labor negotiating mechanisms and Companies such as Bayer responded differently in the US than if the location was a plant in Brazil. At this time a review of a new Bayer plant in Trenton, New Jersey designed by the Austin Company was published in the Architectural Record in august 1948 and mentions no recreational provision.³⁴

It is also interesting that Reids 1951 selection of Architectural Record Industrial reviews and articles in the previous decade include two examples of in-

dustrial plants from Latin America by local architects but which include no recreation provision. From Argentina the Architectural Record published a review of the State Petroleum Company YPF (Yacimientos Petroliferos Federales) Research Laboratories in Florencio Varela by the architects Jorge de la Maria Prins, Hugo M.Rosso, Jorge M. Verbrugge and Jorge R.Martin. This project included museum type presentations of this industry and exhibited other features including the public relations appeal of the new CIAM and Le Corbusion modernist esthetic but with no recreation facilities on site.³⁵ Another architectural project for a new Hoffman La Roche pharmaceutical plant in Rio de Janeiro by the architect Louis Parnes was reviewed by the Architectural Record in march 1947. Parnes design emphasizes modernist advances in luminosity control by the use of the *bris soleir* and the use of glass louvers to assist natural cross ventilation all aimed at the tropical environment portrayed in impressionistic terms in the architects perspectives which accompany the reviewed project.³⁶ But no recreational facilities were apparent. see Fig.15

Another factory project in Guarulhos, São Paulo on the other side of the Dutra Highway near Niemeyers Duchen biscuit factory in 1956 was a new Olivetti typewriter factory by the italian architect Marco Zanuso. The factories peculiar form in part is an immediate design response to the needs imposed by a tropical climate with the ample provision of natural ventilation and structural towers integrated in isosceles triangular column spacing which permitted long production lines along the longest side of the factory site. see Fig.16 Long production line fabrication processes were also the hallmark of the architectural form chosen by another italian architect Giancarlo Palanti, responsible for a new shoe factory for the São Paulo Alpargatas company and built in São José dos Campos in 1958. Penedo mentions the fact that Palanti was a partner in a São Paulo design firm 'Arte Palma' during the 1950's together with the more famous Lina Bo Bardi.³⁷ see Fig.17 But in both of these factory projects by italian architects no recreational facilities were apparent at the time of conception. It could be termed ironic to state that by the end of the century both of these factories would finally be converted into a certain type of recreation in the not necessarily commercial functions of shopping centers. It should be mentioned in the case of the Alpargatas shoe factory one employee facility included in the project was a kindergarten for the plants female employees located beside the main portal entrance. Other employee facilities in other projects sometimes seem to limited the "lean and mean" tendency that seemed to come with the

Fig. 15 – Hoffman La Roche pharmaceutical plant in Rio de Janeiro by the architect Louis Pernes 1947.

Fig. 16 – Olivetti typewriter factory Guarulhos SP architect Marco Zanuso

Fig. 17 – shoe factory for Alpargatas company São José dos Campos SP architect Giancarlo Palanti 1958.

fordism of american design ideas. Going back to Niemeyers and Uchoa's paradigmatic project in the Duchen biscuit factory, it is interesting to note the presence of a separate workers canteen and rest area in a peculiar organic form which tends to negate the long linear production space. see Fig.9.

In conclusion it can be seen from mid-century factory architecture in São Paulo and Rio de Janeiro that many aspects of the Fordist rationalized factory architecture did appear in Brazil. But this was not quite the Fordism as seen in Detroit or as seen in some European intellectual appreciations of Fordism as registered before the 2nd World War. From his prison viewpoint in fascist Italy at the end of the 1920's Antony Gramsci presented one eulogy of fordism in the following general terms: *"In America rationalisation has determined the need to elaborate a new type of man suited to the new type of work and productive process. This elaboration is still only in its initial phase and therefore (apparently) still idyllic. It is still at the stage of psycho-physical adaptation to the new industrial structure, aimed for through high wages."*

In Brazil, 'high-wage fordism' at the end of the XXth century still seems to be paralysed at the "pre-initial" stage while advanced Taylorism has proved not quite *idyllic*. What arrived in São Paulo, in the 1930's and 1940's, seems to have been a "stripped down" version of Fordism, or a "CKD" version to use an analogy from the auto industry. The version assembled in São Paulo was somewhat different from the Norte-american and even European versions given the different labor histories. In Brazil, new labor laws with the CLT, a minimum salary and heavily repressed trade-unions in the 1940's gave way to a tendency for americanized factory planning in the 1950's aimed more at the establishment rather than transformation of industrial production. Green field sites abounded on urban peripheral territory along regional highways for new import-substitution industrial sectors. The 'surge' of industrialization in the 1950's became too readily apparent in the "speeding up" of migratory flows, of metropoltan demographic growth rates, and in a wider sense the countries urbanization. For Volkswagen arriving in 1953 the Via Anchieta plant had little on site recreation and the giant car-parks were more used as open air warehousing facilities for finished and partially finished products subject to wide macro-economic market and trade fluctuations than for workers arriving in their own cars coming off the express-ways. In adapting to local development conditions VW at least began a consumers cooperative for employees in the commercial center of São Bernardo to economize on the limited Brazilian fordist salary.

However, for factory workers in the ABC district of the São Paulo metropolis, working in the new Fordist

and Ford plants along the Via Anchieta Highway in the 1950's there were to be no cars but only the essentials - hired factory bussing and plant feeding, when absolutely necessary. The military government in the 1960's helped massify industrial production with new financial hire-purchase economics providing a means of market expansion, though more for a growing urban middle class than a Fordist emerging labor aristocracy. The reemergence of a militant factory based trade unionism at the end of the 1970's did tend to raise salaries and widen tertiary employment markets but in the local economy of industrial urban areas such as ABC but the economic recessions of the 1980's qualified this militancy while reinforcing a trade-union-management 'confrontation with negotiation' pattern often modeled on N.American labor-management "lean and mean" relations particularly after the 1988-1993 recession.

Industrial innovations in Brazil during the 1990's appears part of another historical period of intense and rapid change. It is tempting to cite again Gramsci's controversial view of the beginnings of Fordism. Talking about the United States in the 1920's Gramsci noted:

"Since these preliminary conditions existed, already rendered rational by historical evolution, it was relatively easy to rationalise production and labour by a skilful combination of force (destruction of working class trade unionism on a territorial basis) and persuasion (high wages, various social benefits, extremely subtle ideological and political propaganda) and thus succeed in making the whole life of the nation revolve around production. Hegemony here is born in the factory and requires for its exercise only a minute quantity of professional political and ideological intermediaries"

In Brazil at the end of the century the nation appears not quite sure about what it is revolving around and certainly the techniques of organising political hegemony have changed in certain formal senses. But at least Gramsci's conception of force and persuasion does still appear relevant at least for discussion. At least fifteen years after micro-electronic innovation began its introduction on the modernist factory floor, the discussion of the high-salary technique of Fordist persuasion seems to run in Brazil in an opposite direction, even with the supposed benefits of a suddenly discovered "new" economy. New factory plants in radically new locations within Brazil permit the forceful establishment of much lower salary levels than those achieved in ABC paulista. What is unclear is the role of low salaries being seen as a necessary competitive injunction for operating in a Brazilian market or as a starting off benchmark for future com-

pany and trade-union relations which should evolve slowly and gradually, with improving urbanization living standards, towards higher salaries for fewer industrial employees. The existing tendency of industrial reorganization in Brazil has exhibited an American Fordist paternity with a characteristic of being "lean and mean" especially in labor relations. The urban consequences may not be pleasant.

NOTES

¹ Frederick J. Woodbridge (Architect - Evans, Moore & Woodbridge) JAN.1941 "Industrial Practice Disciplines the Architect in Kenneth Reid (Ed.) "Industrial Buildings - The Architectural Record of a Decade", New York, F.W.Dodge Corp., 1951, pp.28-29

² Albert Kahn, Architect "Producer Of Production Lines" Architectural Record, June 1942 in Reid, 1951, *ibid.* 257-259

³ Geurst, Jeroen e Futagawa, Yukio "J.A.Brinkman and L.C. Van der Vlugt - Van Nelle Factory, Rotterdam, The Netherlands 1925-31", Tokyo, ADA Edita, 1994.

⁴ Wank, Ronald A. (Associate Felheimer and Wagner, Architects and Engineers) "the Architects Opportunities in Factory Design", Architectural Record, August 1947 In Kenneth Reid, 1951, *op.cit.* pp.178-180.

⁵ Sharp, Denis & Futagawa, Yukio "Walter Gropius Bauhaus, Dessau, Germany, 1925-26 Fagus factory, Alfeld-an-der-Line, Germany 1911-25(with Adolf Meyer", Tokyo, ADA Edita, 1994.

⁶ An Arch.Record Case Study Feb.1940 Chemical Factory, in Buckinghamshire, England Raymond McGrath, A.R.I.B.A., architect which commented the presentation of the case: "Started shortly before hostilities broke out in Europe this factory contains numerous provisions for recreation and comfort, as well as a system of air-raid shelters, all for employees benefit." In Kenneth Reid, 1951, *op.cit.* p. 19

⁷ see "Design for mass production". The Architectural Record. Feb.1940. in Reid *ibid.*p.1

⁸ H.K.Ferguson "New Techniques meet Changed Conditions Economically" jan. 1941 in Reid, 1951, *op.cit.* pp.36-37

⁹ *ibid.* p.37

¹⁰ For this architects contemporary industrial work see Kahn,A. "the Architect Working in Industry", Architectural Record, March 1941 in Reid, 1951, pp416-417, and Kahn,A. Architect "Producer Of Production Lines" Architectural Record, June 1942 in Reid, 1951, 257-259.

¹¹ Among other factory projects the following projects were reviewed in the Architectural Record, were the following: De Soto Employment and Welfare building, Chrysler Corp., Detroit, Michigan Albert Kahn Inc., architects and engineers Feb.1940, *ibid.* p.24.

Ohio Steel Foundry Co.building, Albert Kahn Assoc. Inc. Architects & Engineers Jan 1941 in Reid, 1951,*ibid.* p.34-35,

Toledo Scale Company Factory at Toledo, Ohio published by the AR journal in February 1941 *ibid.*p.4-8

Willow Run Bomber Plant for the Ford Motor Company Albert Kahn Assoc. Inc. Architects & Engineers AR Sept.1942. *ibid.*p.271-278.

Curtiss Wright Aircraft Plant, Columbus Ohio Albert Kahn Assoc. Inc. Architects & Engineers AR Nov.1944.

*ibid.*p.282-287.

Pratt & Whitney Aircraft Engine Plant, Kansas City Albert Kahn Assoc. Inc. Architects & Engineers AR journal February 1945, *ibid.* pp.288-295.

Automobile Factory Chevrolet-Flint Assembly Plant, Flint, Michigan Albert Kahn Associated Architects and Engineers Architectural Record August 1948 *ibid.* pp.200-205.

¹² Ford,H. n/date *op.cit.* p.135.

¹³ Alfred P.Sloan Jr., "My Years with General Motors," New York, 1963 (portuguese version)"Minha Vida na General Motors - Relato Pessoal do antigo diretor principal da maior companhia Manufatura do mundo", Distribuidora Record, 1965.

¹⁴ Ford,*op.cit.*p.286.

¹⁵ Reid, 1951, *op.cit.* p.9

¹⁶ Albert Kahn Associated Architects and Engineers Study for Mill and Factory and the Architectural Record "Factory Design for Low-cost Production" (AR nov.1945) in Reid, 1951 p.141

¹⁷ Unwin, H.D. "Industrial Piping" Architectural Record Feb.1943, in Reid *ibid.* p.485

¹⁸ see Reid 51 *op.cit.*,p.343.

¹⁹ *ibid.* p.143.

²⁰ *ibid.* 155.

²¹ *ibid.* pp. 24,74,75, 82,257 among the factory projects designed by the Kahn practise reviewed by the Architectural Record were the following:

, Willow Run plant Ford, Albert Kahn Associated, Chevrolet-Flint Assmby Plant, Flint Michigan August 1948.

²² Gramsci, Antonio "Selections from the prison notebooks", London, Lawrance & Wishart, 1971, p.298.

²³ The car industries arriving in São Bernardo in the fifties had a close relationship with new petrol refineries, petro-chemical and steel plants in the neighbouring ABC and Cubatão local authority areas. see Gunn, 1992.

²⁴ Crawford,Margaret "Building the Workingmans Paradise : The Design of American Company Towns", London, Haymarket,) Verso Books, 1996.

²⁵ Buchanan, Colin "Traffic in Towns", Harmondsworth, Penguin, 1963.

²⁶ Albert Kahn (Associated Architects ir Engineers, Inc.) "'WARSPEED" system of construction in concrete. as first used for a new aircraft plant", Architectural Record December 1942, in Reid p.72,73,82.

²⁷ Penedo,Alexandre "Arquitetura Moderna São José dos Campos", São José dos Campos, A.Penedo, 1997, pp.29-50.

²⁸ Xavier,Alberto, Lemos,Carlos & Carona,Eduardo "Arquitetura Moderna Paulistana", São Paulo, Ed.Pini, 1983.

²⁹ Reid,1951,*op.cit.*,418-9.

³⁰ see Lopes, Alberto Costa "A Aventura da Cidade Industrial de Tony Garnier em Volta Redonda", Rio de Janeiro, Masters Dissertation, UFRG Geography, 1993, p. 81.

³¹ Unwin, R. (1909) "Town Planning in Practise - an introduction to the art of designing cities and suburbs", T.Fisher Unwin, London, 2ed.1911.

³² Roland Wank Associate, Felheimer & Wagner, Architects and Engineers, "Industrial Buildings - the Plant as a Place to work",

Architectural Record Building Types Study No.120. De-

ember 1946 In Collaboration with "Mill and Factory" in Reid 1951 op.cit pp.157-160.

³³ Ackel, Luis Gonzaga Montans "'Atílio Correa Lima: um urbanista brasileiro 1930-1943", São Paulo, dissertação de mestrado Univ.de Mackenzie, 1996, pp.177-178.

³⁴ ibid, p.214

³⁵ "YPF" (Yacimientos Petroliferos Federales) Research Laboratories in Florencio Varela in Reid, 1951, p.368-75.

³⁶ ibid p.376-9

³⁷ Penedo,1997,op.cit. p.154

BIBLIOGRAPHY AND ILLUSTRATION SOURCES:

Ackel, Luis Gonzaga Montans "'Atílio Correa Lima: um urbanista brasileiro 1930-1943", São Paulo, dissertação de mestrado Univ.de Mackenzie, 1996.

Buchanan, Colin "Traffic in Towns", Harmondsworth, Penguin, 1963

Crawford,Margaret "Building the Workingmans Paradise : The Design of American Company Towns", London, Haymarket,) Verso Books, 1996.

Geurst, Jeroen e Futagawa, Yukio "J.A.Brinkman and L.C. Van der Vlugt – Van Nelle Factory, Rotterdam, The Netherlands 1925-31", Tokyo, ADA Edita, 1994.

Gramsci, Antonio "Selections from the prison notebooks", London, Lawrance & Wishart, 1971, p.298.

Gunn, Philip. "' Uma Nova Geografia Industrial Emergente: um Prognóstico da Economia Urbana em São Bernardo de Campo" São Paulo, 1992, mimeo.

Lopes, Alberto Costa "A Aventura da Cidade Industrial de Tony Garnier em Volta Redonda", Rio de Janeiro, Masters Dissertation, UFRG Geography, 1993.

Manera, Roberto "São Paulo 110 anos de industrialização – 1914-1929", São Paulo, Gráfica do Estado, 1991.

Menezes, José Luiz Mota e Rodrigues, Maria do Rosário Rosa Rodrigues "Fortificações Portuguesas no Nordeste do Brasil – séculos XVI, XVII e XVIII", Recife, Pool Editora, 1986.

Penedo,Alexandre "Arquitetura Moderna São José dos Campos", São José dos Campos, A.Penedo, 1997.

Reid, Kenneth (Ed.) "Industrial Buildings – The Architectural Record of a Decade", N.York, F.W.Dodge, 1951.

Sharp, Denis & Futagawa, Yukio "Walter Gropius Bauhaus, Dessau, Germany, 1925-26 Fagus factory, Alfeld-an-der-Line, Germany 1911-25 (with Adolf Meyer", Tokyo, ADA Edita, 1994.

Sloan Jr. Alfred P., "My Years with General Motors," New York, 1963 (portuguese version)"Minha Vida na General Motors - Relato Pessoal do antigo diretor principal da maior companhia Manufatura do mundo", Distribuidora Record, 1965.

Unwin, R. (1909) "'Town Planning in Practise - an introduction to the art of designing cities and suburbs", T.Fisher Unwin, London, 2ed.1911.

Xavier,Alberto, Lemos,Carlos & Carona,Eduardo "Arquitetura Moderna Paulistana", São Paulo, Ed.Pini, 1983.

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